

Why Compliance Length of Stay (LOS) is the Stronger Outcome Measure than Crude LOS in DRG Systems

Christoph Napierala^{1*}

Abstract

The paper shows that often used evaluation dimensions in health care policy evaluation have to be carefully chosen. Effect measurement depends on it and accordingly drives results. We make our case using Length of Stay (LOS) as an example of a dependent variable and the improved LOS compliance ratio.

Keywords

Length of Stay(LOS) — LOS Compliance — DRG — Prospective Payment Systems — Outcome Variable — Performance Measurement

¹Center for Health, Policy and Economics (CHPE), Universität Luzern

*Correspondence: christoph.napierala@stud.unil.ch

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1. Background

In patient group-related reimbursement systems, and, more specifically, the Diagnosis-Related Groups (DRG) systems, several indicators have been used to measure the effect of their implementation in healthcare financing. The most prominent ones are costs in all their facets [1–4], the associations between costs and quality [5–8], and length of stay (LOS) [9–11]. Furthermore, publications of the European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies [12] examined several countries at the same time, but they always compared absolute indicators with their development through time.

In all these observations LOS has played a central role in measuring efficiency. However it is also contested as the optimal duration for a certain type of patient is unclear [13], and thus there is no general understanding of an efficient baseline value of LOS neither in surgical or in internal disciplines. On the other hand it allows for a transparent overview of the inpatient capacities used in a public health care system. One can deduce for example the number of beds required. Thus it provides a direct overview of the intensity of infrastructure usage.

Absolute outcome variables allow for crude comparisons of varying sizes of the measure itself (e.g.,

the LOS). The aforementioned literature oftentimes relies primarily on such indicators. However, this poses problems as soon as their definition is altered across time. As such, the sole baseline value cannot be compared. For example, LOS definitions per patient group can change from year to year through the alterations of diagnosis or treatments attribution to the specific composition of a patient group.

On the other hand, relative measures account for these issues. Though potentially using the same baseline, they explicitly integrate a comparing element that serves as a reference. One can refer to a catalog value (e.g., yearly reference values) and relate them to an effective value. Specifically, we will use a ratio that combines the Swiss DRG reference catalog value of the LOS and the effective value of days accounted for by hospitals.

We will show with an applied example that findings, especially in the policy area, can be severely distorted by using either a relative or an absolute measure. This potentially leads to wrong conclusions and flawed decisions. We argue that a thorough analysis of the appropriate outcome measure prevents wrong inferences and complements decision-making in a profound way. We will show in our discussion that crude or absolute measures versus relative or benchmark variables impact the results. Thus, this study highlights the importance of the choice of measures applied in policy discussions.

The example used will compare the LOS with a built ratio of the compliance of the length of stay (LOSC). We will show their difference in a current policy discussion and point out the relevance of using a relative, ratio-oriented measure to present policy implementation effects. To our knowledge, little research has been devoted to the study of a critical assumption of the outcome measure in the model.

This paper aims to inform this debate and develop recommendations for improving and monitoring health-care policies by providing a relevant discussion of outcome measurements and its influence on policy effects.

In the next paragraph, we will highlight the most relevant elements distinguishing both types of outcome measures.

2. Absolute and Relative Outcomes

In the epidemiological literature (e.g. [14]), commonly used effect measures are split into two categories based upon the research of [15]. In their view, they allow the appraisal of public health significance for absolute measures while also helping assess apparent effects, classification, or hints at the importance of effects overall for relative measures.

Most commonly, factors like mortality and health-care expenditures are compared across time using crude metrics (i.e., a baseline value). Even rates of change are being compared without highlighting the differences in interpretation and potential caveats related to the use of either rate.

Absolute measures or variables allow for a comparison across time by either looking at the crude development or by measuring the change rates. It is demanding to interpret results because the indicators contain information that has to be made transparent at each moment in time. Because the definition or underlying assumptions change, the interpretation of the face value changes, too. By itself, an absolute ratio therefore has no meaning and requires interpretation. Relative measures, by their nature, address this specific issue by using a reference value to smooth the baseline. As the dimension of absolute measures are dissolved, comparisons become possible without needing to focus on the baseline's value interpretation. In general terms, when relative measures are applied, one seeks to compare performance or other result dimensions directly. In healthcare, for example, this occurs when you intend to compare healthcare provision regions, providers of all kinds, or system comparisons overall. Time series are compared by using generally agreed upon values and referring them to a benchmark or referral value, which was the case in our example in which a DRG reference catalog was employed. In the literature, the focus on relative and absolute outcome measures are rare. In particular, [16] showed the frequency of using of either type in the literature without transparency and why they are being used. However, [17] made it clear that the specific measure influences conclusions that are drawn, especially in a health inequality context. They also refer to an overall level of outcome being relevant for the validity of both types of measures. Absolute measures also tend to include unobserved, external factors that are difficult to eliminate. Although the measure's scale appears to be clear, its factual content depends on the baseline and its compilation. Absolute measures depend on the definition of the aggregate values they represent. For

example, if you compare absolute values for the LOS per patient group or DRG, their content can change, thus making the comparability of the single values challenging. Using a reference value like the average LOS contained in the DRG catalog combined with the LOS of the single case, one avoids this issue. The relative ratio is then compared, for example, through time, losing focus on the absolute face value of the measure and enabling a solid comparison possibility on performance. Ratios that basically lose their original dimension have the disadvantage of needing a normative statement for their interpretation. Interpreting high and low values of a ratio and respective thresholds can be difficult to define, and it is highly context-sensitive. We will in the next part take a closer look at LOS and its relevance for our discussion.

3. Length of Stay (LOS)

In general terms LOS measure the length of an inpatient stay in a hospital. It is measured by the difference of the admission and dismissal time of the patient. It is normally measured in full days. Commonly if a patient stays at the hospital passing midnight this is counted as one day (i.e. midnight census), this method is for example also applied in Switzerland. An alternative calculus could be the number of hours a patient is registered in the hospital.

The obvious advantage of measuring LOS lies in its ease and objective way of counting. It also has a role in the consideration of hospital expenditure where it is multiplied with the number of admissions and the cost of stay per day [13]. With this definition it makes a prime measure for efficiency comparisons within and among hospitals. Comparing the raw measure through time gives a transparent overview on its development. It also allows for direct conclusions and calculus of required infrastructure (e.g. hospital beds for inpatients) and human resource requirements. But it can, for example, also highlight or support other effects like the ones related to the subject of bloody exits [2].

Nevertheless the disadvantage of it are that with the differing definitions of its calculus. But also the changing composition be it either the attribution of diagnostic or treatment cases to one patient group or be it the weight of cases per group through these changes. Due to the dynamics in the DRG catalog, cases will fluctuate significantly. In the Swiss context the catalog's case weight face value of a DRG can change yearly. If one wants to ensure comparability along the timeline a common baseline definition has to be found and all the cases have to be re-coded using for example a reference indicator similar to the chosen normalization approach in [18]. The drawback is the potential loss of a substantial number of cases that are not codeable and thus potentially biasing the overall result. As such the raw measure could be misleading in the short run because it is not able to distinguish long-term effects like displayed in [19].

The next section will explain the relevance and

construction of the LOSC.

4. LOS Compliance (LOSC)

The fallacies of the LOS as indicator require some rethinking and leads to the here below developed discussion about LOSC.

In general, the LOS reference (ALOS)¹ value is calculated by SwissDRG from the Swiss Case Mix Office. It represents all accumulated Swiss hospitals LOS values averaged by DRG and year. The calculated ratio ($LOSC_{compliance} = LOSC$) does relate the individual LOS per DRG with the Average Length of Stay (ALOS) provided in the catalog.

$$LOSC_{DRG_i} = ALOS_{DRG_{CH_i}} / LOS_{DRG_i}$$

where i represents the specific DRG. This ratio variable reflects the rate of the hospital's compliance to the catalog's reference value (i.e., ALOS for Switzerland). This should also be a means to exclude fixed effects stemming from characteristics by specific hospitals or other factors that might influence absolute values. In contrast, here we observe a relationship instead. In a simplified manner, this rate allows for evaluating the efficiency of a hospital. Good processes and clinical productivity are reflected by higher values.² Overall a hospital should strive to obtain a high relative ratio. This ratio could also be used as a proxy for quality in hospitals. This assumes that a patient being dismissed is cured and that the speed of treatment ("ceteris paribus") represents a sign of qualitative healthcare provisioning.

Implicitly, a hospital's interest is to execute their clinical activities with, for example, a better cost ratio than what the average does in order to gain a competitive advantage. If we assume that hospitals search for excellence in optimizing the utilization of their resources, we can also do so for their simultaneous search for increasing their clinical quality. Such hospitals will also strive to reduce the readmission rates. Thus aiming at treating patients with an appropriate level of care by optimizing both costs and quality.

The above mentioned subject of measuring earlier than medically advised dismissals (e.g. bloody exits) is still possible thanks to the ratio's definition. The loss of the dimension of the crude LOS rate within the LOSC ratio however allows for a more objective appreciation of the development or performance comparison of the assessed institution or entity. Therefore, we will continue with the hypothesis that the LOSC is a proxy for quality beyond process quality.

Naturally, several explanatory dimensions can apply. However, for our analysis and context, this basic framework should be robust enough using the LOSC. The LOSC can also be relevant with respect to an overall healthcare production function. One can assume

that the better (i.e. the higher) the ratio is, the more economically patients are being treated overall. This would enhance the overall public health situation by being more efficient and spending less resources on the same level of healthcare services. For our purpose, this indicator helps enhance the analysis of only using the LOS.³

In general ratios can measure operational efficiency, liquidity, stability, and profitability, but in our case, it can also put the length of stay (denominator, i.e. LOS) in relation to a benchmark, which is the DRG catalog's reference value of the LOS (nominator, i.e. ALOS). Intentionally, we apply the ratio counterintuitively where the ALOS would be put into the denominator and LOS in the nominator in order to show the performance of a value compared to a benchmark. With this we aim at an enhanced interpretation of the ratio where the reciprocal LOSC rates correspond to higher values of the ratio instead of the converse. This allows us to provide more relevant information than just the raw LOS data. Moreover, it can directly reveal trends, whereas absolute measures clearly fail in this respect. The Swiss DRG system has the advantage that it provides an implicit benchmark through the Swiss wide average values of the LOS. Other countries might not have a pre-calculated reference, so it would have to be developed or other references would have to be found.

The advantage by applying the ratio as an outcome variable, we avoid the issue of the unstable LOS factor by assuming that the proportion between the effectively used LOS and the cataloged average LOS will represent a robust comparison throughout time. Thus, the ratio measure has clear advantages by enabling a comparison of groups (i.e., treatment versus non-treatment) without needing technical amendments or altering the baseline values by re-coding a full data set. It enhances trend analysis for smaller units by not requiring a long time series. The ratio itself can be further used as a quality proxy. However, the interpretation and, especially, the use as proxy for comparing clinical quality among service providers has to be done carefully as stated in the literature [21]. Adjustments like weighting for case mix indexes are especially relevant. Similar to our attempt, the authors propose a ratio between expected and observed values, solving the intricacies of the crude LOS value. What we claim in our ratio is that one can relax these requirements by using a ratio.

Most likely, one of the largest drawbacks of using the LOSC is that, as an average value (i.e., average LOS), it implicitly contains the cases that have contributed to the mean during the year before. This endogeneity has to be accounted for in this argument using the ratio. Still, it is not clear how to control for this fact and whether it really overestimates the effect of the policy intervention itself. We, therefore, affirm our hypothesis that the ratio's utility outweighs

¹ Normally, these values represent averages per patient or diagnostic group; however, the aggregation level only plays a role in the interpretation of the ratio in comparison.

² As mentioned above, this is normative and depends on how the ratio is being built and the nature of the respective sides.

³ Compare [20] for an earlier analysis on policy effects using LOS where the difficulties of only using LOS become apparent

this negative aspect. Furthermore the development of the LOS is still implicitly contained in the ratio. Thus a some of the ratios size resides in the numerator. Additionally such a relative measure becomes more difficult to be constructed if there is no readily available comparator. At last, and more from a theoretical perspective, the denominator can take extreme, both small and large, values and thus the interpretation of the ratio becomes challenging. But those cases represent exceptions overall and do have explainable sources or can even represent measurement errors.

The next paragraph will formally display how the ratio is derived and present some descriptive evidence on the magnitude and change rates through time.

5. Brief Discussion

The data summarized in the table below 1 stem from the Swiss medical statistics database (2011 to 2013), and the table contains all DRG cases for the University Hospitals in Switzerland. Each DRG case has been matched with the yearly catalog data. From this, the LOSC ratio has been built.

Table 1 displays the LOS and LOSC for the available semesters with the number um cases, their mean, and deviation measures. The interesting factor is the change in the mean where the LOSC for the first semester of 2012 shows a substantial decrease over all numbers compared to the LOS in which only a small effect can be observed. Knowing that the Swiss DRG was implemented early that semester and that change rates before and after are far smaller, we conclude that the policy change has had an impact on the hospital system’s efficiency in Switzerland. Because we only focus on the application of the LOSC, we will not investigate further into the reasons. What we also exclude is a pure "catalog effect" because we refer every year to its respective catalog and, thus, do not compare the respective DRG’s LOS change, but solely the change in the dimensionless ratio. As such, the ratio compares a "normalized" value.

	Year & Semester	n	mean	sd	se	% Change in mean
Length of Stay (LOS)	2011S1	63267	6.66	7.29	0.02898	
	2011S2	61560	6.63	7.31	0.02946	-0.45%
	2012S1	65077	6.52	7.16	0.02807	-1.66%
	2012S2	63999	6.52	7.22	0.02854	0.00%
	2013S1	66380	6.43	7.16	0.02779	-1.38%
	2013S2	66559	6.31	7.09	0.02748	-1.87%
Compliance of LOS (LOSC)	2011S1	63267	2.31	1.80	0.00716	
	2011S2	61560	2.33	1.79	0.00721	0.87%
	2012S1	65077	2.01	1.73	0.00678	-13.73%
	2012S2	63999	2.05	1.75	0.00692	1.99%
	2013S1	66380	2.00	1.73	0.00671	-2.44%
	2013S2	66559	2.04	1.76	0.00682	2.00%

Table 1: LOS vs. LOSC Highlighting Effect Difference

One of the most relevant features of the relative ratio appears in Figure 1. Here, we can see the dependence of the outcome and number of treatments on either the LOS (left panel) or LOSC (right panel). As expected, we see in the left panel that the LOS

increases with the number of treatments. In contrast, the LOSC decreases steadily, but only from a certain threshold onward. However, the interesting area of investigation is the behavior until that breaking point. Because we assume that the more treatments the patient gets, the less the catalogs value is achievable, the ratio is therefore reduced across time.

Figure 1: Outcome Compared to Number of Treatments

The descriptive evidence indicates that efficiency levels are maintained up to a certain level, and after a threshold performance, they are reduced with an increasing number of treatments. That factor could indicate obtaining a certain "efficiency" level from which a decrease will occur. However, this is not the current scope of investigation. This example shows that both indicators, despite the same baseline, display different developments. This allows the refining of interpretation possibilities.

In the appendix in section 6, other factors were added, including the artificial respiration hours shown in Figure 2. The stay in the intensive care unit (ICU in Figure 4) shows similar patterns compared with both indicators. This is in contrast to the number of diagnoses Figure 3, which is close to being perfectly inversely related.

Those factors only support our claim that the relative ratio indicator depicts the effective behavior more correctly because it attempts to integrate a reference or benchmark value. Thus, this "normalizes" the baseline indicator, which enables a refined and more robust assessment of the overall situation. We claim that with this novel approach, we can obtain a direct measure of efficiency and performance in an inpatient hospital setting in contrast to the baseline value alone. If we were using the LOS as a sole comparing factor as in [22], we would have to re-code⁴ the DRG cases to one reference year in order to make the cases comparable. We disregard bias through adapted behaviors in clinical practice. With the compliance ratio, we avoid this technical and content challenge.

However, we need to account for eventual normative interpretations for the LOSC. This is because one could interpret higher ratio values as a sign of good process quality and clinical efficiency. Using it as a proxy for quality in hospitals, both process and clinical

⁴ I.e., regroup with the Swiss-DRG grouper tool.

perspectives show its advantage over the absolute LOS value. In effect, this assumes that if the individual hospital is above or below the average, either the quality or efficiency of the service provision is different from the benchmark value of that specific patient treatment expressed by the same DRG. Currently, we have no evidence for the reliability of this assumption, which could represent a limitation in our discussion. It appears to be plausible, but more research would be needed.

What factors have to be mentioned, and what can we conclude after our comments and evaluation of the outcome measures?

6. Limitations and Conclusion

Some of the limitations have already been mentioned in the previous sections, and they will not all be reiterated. However, the normative dimension has to be mentioned again. While the use of the LOSC avoids issues related to the absolute measurement of outcomes, it also presents problems that are inherent to the value. One issue could be a dynamic reference value in the denominator. Thus, one has to be careful using the respective reference and interpreting it correctly. Our current example illustrates this well. It would lead to biased conclusions by employing the same base (i.e., only comparing the LOS per DRG) all along the time series due to the catalog's value, which is adapted every year. Thus, one would be comparing a moving base. On the other hand, high and low values for the LOSC have to be clearly described or their distribution has to be mentioned in order to avoid bias in the interpretation. Additionally, the denominator of the relative ratio has to be carefully assessed in order to normalize the raw value and make it properly comparable throughout time.

Moreover, the relative LOSC measure allows us to assess differences between healthcare providers without requiring further information regarding the specific characteristics of the institution. Alternatively, the measure hints at structural differences directly. In particular, the patient groups will reflect upon the value itself. A highly specialized hospital that treats a limited type of patients (e.g., specialized orthopedic hospitals) by nature have a restricted variety of DRG cases. Thus, they can focus on clinical process quality. In contrast, hospitals with a much broader clinical portfolio (i.e., a much higher caseload) and more prominent internal medicine department do struggle in being as efficient, and, thus, have lower LOSC ratios. Thus, one can see that the indicator's level already provides information that the crude LOS would fail to provide.

In some cases like ours, absolute and relative measures may diverge with respect to the magnitude or direction of change. Conclusions might be difficult to interpret and require a solid understanding of the interpretative space.

In recent literature, no systematic assessment of how this influences findings and decisions has been undertaken. A substantially better systematic review, to

our knowledge, would be required to determine which measure type should be used. Such a comprehensive article on the basics beyond the scope of this discussion will improve usage of appropriate outcome measures in policy decisions and the measurement of causal relationships.

Appendix

Figure 2: Outcome Compared to Art.Res.Hours

Figure 3: Outcome Compared to Number of Diagnosis

Figure 4: Outcome Compared to Average Hours ICU

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